

3. A. A. YADAV and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 290.
4. V. M. SHINDE and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1970, 249, 239.
5. W. M. McNABB and J. F. HAZEL, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, 27, 405.
6. W. J. MAECK, M. E. KUSSY and J. E. REIN, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1964, 199, 69.
7. M. N. SASTRI and D. S. SUNDER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1967, 225, 56.
8. G. B. FASOLO, R. MALVRANO and A. MASSAGLIA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1963, 29, 569.
9. D. G. TUCK, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, 27, 296.
10. J. ADAM and R. PRIBIL, *Talanta*, 1971, 18, 91.
11. P. NAGESWARA RAO and K. ADINARAYANA REDDY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 402.
12. N. K. BAISHYA and G. BARUAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 389.
13. V. K. GUPTA and S. G. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 581; 1971, 48, 753.
14. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1962.

Separation and Microdetermination of Nitrate with *N-m-Tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic Acid* (TMBHA)

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NITRATES find their way in water from various sources¹. The presence of excess of nitrates in water causes pollution². Thus, determination of nitrates in water in micro-amounts is essential from the pollution point of view. Several methods have been suggested for the determination of nitrate in water³⁻⁹. Most of the colorimetric determinations are based on the conversion of nitrate in the presence of sulphuric acid into the nitro derivative of phenolic compounds.

In this communication, *N-m-tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic acid* (TMBHA) is proposed for the determination of nitrate in water. The method is based on the extraction of yellow coloured compound formed between nitrate and TMBHA in carbon tetrachloride. The coloured organic layer is measured at 360 nm. The reaction is very sensitive for nitrate determination. Nitrate is clearly separated from various other ions.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric measurements were done in Beckman model DU-2 spectrophotometer with 10

mm matched silica cells. Standard stock solution of potassium nitrate containing 6.2 μg nitrate per ml was prepared in deionized water.

The reagent, TMBHA, was synthesized and purified as reported earlier¹⁰. $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of TMBHA in double distilled carbon tetrachloride (carbon disulphide free) was prepared. Analytical grade sulphuric acid was used.

An aliquot containing less than 12.4 μg nitrate and 5.0 ml 7.2 *M* sulphuric acid was made to 10 ml and allowed to cool to room temperature. This solution was equilibrated with 10 ml $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ TMBHA in carbon tetrachloride for 20 min. The organic layer was collected over anhydrous sodium sulphate and measured at 360 nm against similarly processed reagent blank. The extracted nitrate was determined from the calibration curve.

Application of the method: Water from different local sources was collected. Pretreatment of this water for preparing sample solution was done by standard methods⁹. Water sample was evaporated to an appropriate volume and filtered. 2 ml of this sample solution was taken and nitrate content was determined as mentioned in the general procedure.

Results and Discussion

The yellow coloured extractable species formed between nitrate and TMBHA absorbs maximum at 360 nm.

Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 0.08-1.24 μg nitrate per ml with an optimum range 0.09-0.93 μg of nitrate per ml of carbon tetrachloride. The molar absorptivity was $8.0 \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Sandell's sensitivity was estimated to be 0.0008 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

The effect of acidity was studied over the range 0.1-10.0 *M* sulphuric acid. The colour intensity increases above 2.0 *M* acidity and attains maximum at 3.6 *M*. Beyond 3.6 *M* the absorbance remains constant, but the separation of two layers becomes difficult. Hence, all the measurements were carried out at 3.6 *M* acidity. 10 ml of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ TMBHA was adequate for quantitative extraction of 3.1 μg of nitrate. The absorbance of the complex remained constant for 2 h. A period of 10 min was sufficient for complete extraction.

Effect of foreign ions: The effect of various foreign ions on the extraction behaviour of 3.1 μg nitrate was studied. The tolerance limit was set at the amount of foreign ion to cause $\pm 2\%$ error in the recovery of the nitrate. The results show that fifty fold excess of Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , As^{3+} , As^{5+} , Mo^{6+} , twenty times excess of Cu^{2+} , and five times excess of Fe^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , Co^{2+} do not interfere. Cr^{3+} , Cr^{6+} and W^{6+} are tolerated upto two times excess. BO_3^{3-} and NO_2^- interfere seriously. Fifty times excess of Cl^- , Br^- and ten times excess of I^- do not interfere.

The relative standard deviation from ten determinations was found to be $\pm 1.2\%$.

Application to water samples: The proposed method has been successfully employed in the determination of nitrate content of some water samples obtained from local sources of drinking water. The results of the determinations with and without known additions of nitrate are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF NITRATE IN VARIOUS WATER SAMPLES

Sample	Nitrate, mg, l ⁻¹	
	Added	Found
1	0	64
	50	116
2	0	40
	30	73
3	0	95
	10	107

References

1. J. RODIER, "Analysis of Water", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1975, p. 729.
2. "Standard Methods for the Examination of Water, Sewage and Industrial Waste", 14th ed., American Public Health Association, Inc., 1975.
3. R. MÜLLER and O. WIDEMANN, *Zahr. V. Wasser*, 1975, 22, 249.
4. A. M. HARTLEY and R. I. ASAI, *J. Am. Water Works Assoc.*, 1960, 52, 255, 258.
5. H. A. C. MONTGOMERY and J. F. DYMCK, *Analyst*, 1962, 87, 374, 1034.
6. D. W. W. ANDREWS, *Analyst*, 1964, 89, 730, 1064.
7. R. CARON, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1910, 1, 1021.
8. H. STAISARTH, *Centre Belge d'Elyde et de Documentation des Eaux*, 1967, 281, 183.
9. A. K. BABKO and A. T. PILIPENKO, "Photometric Analysis, Methods of Determination of Non-Metals", Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1976.
10. V. K. GUPTA and S. G. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 267.

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trithiocarbonates and Mercaptans (Through Trithiocarbonate Formation) with Bismuth(III)

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ORGANOTRITHIOCARBONATES (RS.CS.S⁻) are the salts of the corresponding trithiocarbonic acids (RS.CS.SH). The compounds find considerable applications^{1,2} in medicine, agriculture and industry. Their vast commercial use necessitates convenient methods for their analysis. A new and rapid extractive spectrophotometric method has

been developed for the determination of these compounds with bismuth(III). The reagent forms yellow insoluble complexes with these compounds. Chloroform is used for extraction which is quantitative within pH 2-8. The absorbance of the yellow extract is measured at 420 nm against a reagent blank. The method has been successfully extended to the determination of mercaptans after their quantitative transformation into the corresponding trithiocarbonates through reaction with carbon disulphide in the presence of alkali. The proposed method is simple, accurate, widely applicable and may be used for the routine analysis of both trithiocarbonates and mercaptans.

Experimental

Organotrithiocarbonates were prepared and purified as described earlier^{1,2}. The purity of the compounds was checked by an iodometric method⁴. Acetate buffer (pH 4.05) was prepared by mixing 2M solutions of acetic acid and sodium acetate in the ratio 8 : 2 (v/v). Mercaptans were distilled before use. Bausch and Lomb spectrophotometer (Spectronic 20) was used for absorbance measurements. Digital pH meter equipped with glass-calomel combination electrode was used for pH measurements.

Aliquots (0.1-1.0 ml) of the solution in water of each trithiocarbonate were transferred with shaking to bismuth(III) nitrate pentahydrate (1 ml, 0.1M in water) and acetate buffer (1 ml, pH 4.05) added. The volume of each solution was made to 10 ml with water. Chloroform (10 ml) was added and the two phases thoroughly equilibrated for 1 min, and then allowed to settle for 1 min. The absorbance of the organic phase was measured spectrophotometrically at 420 nm against a reagent blank, similarly prepared. Calibration curves were prepared in each case. In the determination of mercaptans, potassium hydroxide (2 ml, ~0.05M in water) and carbon disulphide (0.5 ml, ~1M in acetonitrile) were added to aliquots of the solution of mercaptans in acetonitrile. The solution thus obtained was neutralised with acetic acid (~0.1M in water) and to it were added with shaking bismuth(III) nitrate pentahydrate (1 ml, 0.1M in water) and acetate buffer (1 ml, pH 4.05). The volume of each solution was made to 10 ml with water. Further experimental details were the same as described above for trithiocarbonates.

Results and Discussion

The influence of pH on the degree of extraction was studied by extracting the complexes from a series of aqueous solutions buffered in the pH range 2-8. The absorbance was maximal and constant throughout this range. The measurements were, however, made at pH 4.05. One min shaking was required for maximum colour development in the organic phase. The colour of the complex was